

Supplementary table S1 to the “Comparative assessment of brewers spent grain pretreatment methods suitable for microorganism media production”
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Elemental composition of BSG

(Two batches samples from Aldaris Brewery, Latvia)

Sample name	BSG (K)	BSG (V)
Chemical element	Concentration, mg/(100 g of biomass)	Concentration, mg/(100 g of biomass)
P	702.28	631.37
Ca	382.87	299.84
Si	294.59	372.45
Mg	195.49	186.54
K	68.15	69.82
Fe	16.49	13.78
Zn	9.11	7.68
S	8.93	7.50
Na	5.59	4.42
Mn	4.14	3.47
Al	1.62	3.97
Ba	1.37	1.14
Cu	0.78	0.74
Cr	0.23	0.09
Mo	0.15	0.20
Ti	0.10	0.12
Ni	0.08	0.04
Cd	< LOD*	< LOD
Co	< LOD	< LOD
Li	< LOD	< LOD
Pb	< LOD	< LOD
Sb	< LOD	< LOD
V	< LOD	< LOD

* LOD - limit of detection